

NON-DUAL CONSCIOUSNESS AND QUANTUM ONTOLOGY: A
DIALOGUE BETWEEN BRAHMAN AND FIELD THEORY

* Dr. Saikat Bandyapadhyay

Abstract:

The essay tends to theorize a philosophical doctrine of the long past and contemporary as well, in such form, 'Brahman is true while the world is false.' First, I shall try to explain the observation of Adi-Guru Śaṅkarācārya with regard to the subject and next views of Quantum Physics will be discussed with reference to renowned scientist Mani Bhowmik's publication '*Brahma Satya, Jagat Satya*'. In the third phase, I would like criticize Mr. Bhowmik regarding his views on the Science of Material System and finally, argue in favour of Śaṅkarā's stand.

Keywords: Brahman, Non-dualism, Quantum Physics, Transcendental, Quarks, Electrons, Ultimate Reality

** Assistant Professor, Department of Philosophy, Durgapur Government College*

The proposition 'Brahman is true' is not the bone of contention in the history of the Vedanta. Each and every school of Vedanta accepts Brahman as the Absolute or Ultimate Reality of the Universe though interpretation of different schools is not the same. But the most controversial issue in Vedantic philosophy prevails whether the world is true or not. This is a doctrinal problem which seems me a continuous problem of philosophy as such even today.

We may have four logical possibilities regarding the relation between Brahman and the World. 1) Brahman is true, the world is true; 2) both Brahman and the world are false. 3) Brahman is false while the world is true, 4) Brahman is true while the world is false; Out of these, the first three options are not practicable. If Brahman and the world were true at the same time, no philosophical discourse would have been in existence. Again, as Brahman denotes consciousness, it cannot be false, and, therefore, the second and third propositions are not acceptable.

With regard to the fourth option, it is justifiable to say that the world is not self-revealed and there is duality in everything. From this point of view the world cannot be true. On the other hand, Brahman, being

self-revealed and non-dual consciousness, deserves to be true. Therefore, the only option left is – Brahman is true while the world is false.

Traditional preachers of Vedanta were to establish unanimously the primal existence of Brahman. schools of Vedanta like that of Ramanuja, Madhavacārya, Vallabhacārya and Nimbarka were in support of the view that the world is true apart from Brahman. But Acarya Śaṅkarā did not admit this. He was of the opinion that Brahman itself is true and no other truth exists anywhere. Now ideology of Acarya Śaṅkarā is being described in brief.

Sankara is known to be the profounder of 'Kevaladvaitavada'. In this philosophical concept he accepted three kinds of being or reality viz *Pāramārthika*, *Vyāvahārika* and *Pratibhasika*. This is called 'Sattātrividhavadā'. According to Śaṅkarā, Satya is *Pāramārthika* i.e., ever unobstructed by anything irrespective of time and space. As Brahman is not being obstructed by anything so Satya of Brahman is *Pāramārthika*. He ascribed the word 'True' or 'Sat' to indicate *Pāramārthika* Satya because Brahman is 'True' in Its absolute sense of propagation.

On the other hand, the object of 'Pramā' (true cognition) falls under the category of *Vyāvahārika Satya*. It is very much identical in the perceptible world but with the up rear of the knowledge of Brahman it is being rejected thoroughly. Śaṅkarā used the word 'False' to objectify *Vyāvahārika Satya* as because it has no absolute existence but a relative state of feeling only. Again, *Prātibhāsika*, according to Śaṅkara, is a grand illusion that comes into view out of sense-experience. It cannot be ignored in the apparent world but the seeming objects do have no existence in the world of habitual employment.¹

According to Śaṅkara, Brahman alone is Real or Absolute. He described Brahman from two standpoints—practical or empirical and transcendental or metaphysical.² The first one discloses Brahman as the omniscient and omnipresent creator, sustainer and destructor of the phenomenal world. In this phase Brahman seems to possess varied qualities and dimensions. From this aspect it is called Saguna Brahman or God. It is the object of worship to the devotees. But this concept does not reveal

intrinsic nature of Brahman. It is Brahman, the creator of the universe, seems to be an accidental phenomenon mingled with Maya. Hence it cannot be described as 'Ultimate'.²

From the metaphysical point of view, Brahman, according to Śaṅkarā, is devoid of all qualities and distinctions, either internal or external. Brahman, from this stand-point, is indeterminate or Nirguna. It is being defined as *Sachhidānanda* (*sat, cit* and *ānanda*). Śaṅkarā observed that Brahman i.e. pure consciousness is devoid of all attributes and becomes the Ultimate Reality. This Nirguna Brahman appears to be the qualified or Saguna Brahman and becomes the creator, preserver and destroyer of the practical world with potency called Maya. Brahman is the origin on which the world appears through Maya with its two powers—concealment (*Āvaraṇa*) and projection (*Vikṣepa*). When right knowledge is acquired by Sadhana and incessant unity of *Jīvātman* and *Paramātman* is realized, Maya or Avidya vanishes. 'That Art Thou' (*tat-tam asi*)—the comprehension of Self is regarded as ultimate truth or highest knowledge as

¹Dasgupta, S.N. p. 432, *A History of Indian Philosophy*, Cambridge University Press, 1992, p. 432

² Deussen, P., *The System of Vedanta*, Translated by Charles Johnston/ the Open Court Publishing Company, 1912, Chicago, U.S.A., p.266

because this knowledge, when produced, our cognition of earthly appearance automatically ceases to have its existence.

Thus, Śāṅkarā held that the world is false owing to its relative existence, which, in form of illusion, makes us believe it to be true. The universe, a product of Maya, is indefinite in nature. It is neither *sat* nor *asat*. The world is said to be 'is' or existing since it appears to be so for the time the state of ignorance persists in us. But as soon as right knowledge arises, we come to realize that the ascribable entity of the world has no eternal approach and hence it cannot be depicted as 'true'. Though the world cannot be defined as 'is not' or non-existent, yet Śāṅkarā was not at all agreeable to describe it as 'is' because of its illusive or deceptive nature tending to a mortal end.³ Therefore, the inference has been drawn that the world though exists becomes false in consideration of its ultimate non-existence.

[2]

Now we shall discuss the stand of Quantum Physics as to the concept of the world and the world beyond. Sri Manilal

Bhowmik, a renowned Physicist, has penned down a book named 'Brahma 'Satya Jagat Satya-- Upaniṣad, Vigyan, Rabindranath'. The very name of the book suggests that Brahman as well as the world is true. According to him, Quantum Physics asserts that there are three layers of Reality though we see only one of them. The first layer can be experienced by us while the two others are invisible and abstract. All the physical objects and the phenomenon happening around us are not illusory but are quite real—Sri Bhowmik observes. Actually, we see the upper layer of reality, say, tip of the iceberg. A close look through a powerful microscope will help us see that the iceberg is made of invisible atoms. What is an atom made of? It has nucleus containing the center with electrons around it. A few protons and neutrons are imprisoned in a nucleus and their balance is being maintained by electrons, the negatively-charged atom. If protons are further analysed, we will get some smaller particles of atom which are called Quarks. Everything on the earth, either animate or inanimate, is essentially made of two fundamental

³ Dasgupta, S.N. p. 432, *A History of Indian Philosophy*, Cambridge University Press, 1992, p. 433

particles—quarks and electrons. These fundamental particles have been defined by Einstein as ‘Packages of Energy’. Einstein was of the opinion that matter itself is energy.⁴

Quantum Physics call quarks and electrons ‘fundamental particles’ because these cannot be divided any further. There are a number of other fundamental particles as well, but these are either unstable or feebly interactive. Therefore, Scientists cannot help deal with these particles but under special circumstances such as in the high-energy particle physics laboratory. Though these particles compose earthly matters yet these are not ‘primitive source’ of the universe. Rather, it is the ‘quantum field’ by which fundamental particles i.e. quarks and electrons remain combined. These do not even break down from composite objects. We may compare quantum field with a tight-neck bottle in which the gene remains confined. Similarly, quarks and electrons, though move at the

speed of light, are not out-tracked because of the centripetal force of quantum field.⁵

It may also be pointed out that fundamental particles like electrons are absolutely identical anywhere in the universe, no matter when or where these are being created. Mass, electric charge and spin of these particles always remain the same. This happens only because an all-pervading field creates all these. Prof. Wilczek of MIT (Massachusetts Institute of Technology) asserts, “in quantum field theory, the primary elements of reality are not individual particles but underline fields.”⁶

The fields, being the controller of energy, are really abstract because these are not at all physical or material. For an example, we cannot see the field of gravity of the earth, cannot even touch it, but it is essentially real. Although it is next to impossible to grasp gravity, yet we cannot deny it as the primary source of reality of the universe having its existence in an abstract form. It is evident from the above

⁴ Einstein, Albert. *Relativity: The Special and the General Theory*. Translated by Robert W. Lawson, Henry Holt and Company, 1920.

⁵ Kaku, Michio. *Quantum Field Theory: A Modern Introduction*. Oxford University Press, 1993.

⁶ Wilczek, Frank. *The Lightness of Being: Mass, Ether, and the Unification of Forces*. Basic Books, 2008.

discussion that the first layer of reality is visible and accessible while the second layer is out and out an invisible accumulation of energy governed by the third layer i.e. the primal reality of abstract fields.

It is very important to mention here that we come across a number of fields in nature viz. electric-force field, magnetic-force field, strong and weak nuclear-force field etc. These diversified fields are now being established to be nothing but different aspects of one and only field i.e. Quantum field.⁷ This unified field contains the blueprint of entire universe. Being present in the initial element of space, sequentially it unfolds itself to generate the universe and everything it contains. After generating the cosmos, it is very much present at every distinct fabric of space, determining the underlying aspects of varied phenomenon of the universe.⁸

It is important to note that according to physicists the quantum field, the source of the universe, is pure consciousness. The

pioneers who developed quantum mechanics, Heisenberg and Schrodinger maintain that consciousness is the very basis of all creation. Max Plank, father of the quantum concept, agrees, saying 'I regard consciousness as primary. I regard matter is derivative of consciousness'. In addition, the famous physicist and astronomer Sir Arthur Eddington declared "all through the physical world runs that unknown content which must surely be the stuff of our consciousness."⁹

Prof. Bhowmik has observed that post-modern scientific inventions of quantum physics lend support to the concept: beyond our daily reality. The all-pervading abstract reality in form of quantum field is similar to the concept of Brahman that Vedanta propagates all along. Upaniṣad, one of the elementary works of Vedanta, asserts that Brahman is the all-pervasive being which exists in every particle of the world. The One, omnipotent and omnipresent Brahman, determines rest

⁷ Peskin, Michael E., and Daniel V. Schroeder. *An Introduction to Quantum Field Theory*. Westview Press, 1995, pp. 1-5.

⁸ Michio Kaku. *The God Equation: The Quest for a Theory of Everything*. Doubleday, 2021, pp. 3-12.

⁹ *Katha Upanishad*. Translated by Eknath Easwaran, Nilgiri Press, 2007, p. 23

of the universe immanently. Chhandogya Upaniṣads rightly observed that Brahman remains everywhere (*Sarvang Khalvidang Brahman*). Kathapaniṣad has also aptly stated “*Eko vaṣī sarvabhūtāntarātmā ekaṁ rūpaṁ bahudhā yaḥ karoti.*”¹⁰ This means, worldly objects are being manifested out of the eternal and non-dual Brahman which is nothing but pure consciousness.

So, it is very much evident from the basic concept of Brahman in Vedanta and that in Quantum Physics that an ultimate entity is incessantly present everywhere thereby supporting and governing everything on the earth and also in the universe. Everything changes with the change of time and space except this unified field which may be defined as ‘eternal’ and all-pervading as the Vedantists hold while speaking about Brahman.

[3]

Prof. Bhowmik, a stern follower and propagator of Quantum Physics, supports the Upaniṣadic view of the ultimate reality but does not accept Śaṅkara’s commentary on the Upaniṣads. Śaṅkara held that Brahman is true while the world is false.

¹⁰ Bhowmik, Mani, *Brahmo Satya, Jagat Mithya-Upaniṣad*, Vijyana, Rabindranath Ananda Publisher/ First Publication-2012 / pp. 25

Bhowmik does not agree to this view. He holds that the world is true as the Brahman is. Modern science gives a number of evidence in favour of this theory. As earthly things are made of one source (quantum field), these are as true as the source. When the origin is true, substance arising from it cannot be false. Prof. Bhowmik accuses that Śaṅkara’s observation would have probably been weakened the history of Indian civilization by making worldly affairs inactive and unaccountable.¹¹

Prof. Bhowmik further adds that distinguished persons like Tagore, Vivekananda and Rammohan did not accept the world as false. When we go through the poem “*Rupnarayaner kule / Jege uthilum / Janilum e jagat / Swapna noy*”—it becomes clear to us that Rabindranath was very much aware of earthly affairs. Again “*Param amir sange jukto hote pari / vichitra jagat e / prabesh lovite pari anander pathe*” – these lines from the desk of Tagore distinctly disclose the world as an activated zone of liveliness.

Rammohan Roy, the pioneer of modern India and the renaissance of Bengal,

¹¹ Bhowmik, Mani, *Brahmo Satya, Jagat Mithya-Upaniṣad*, Vijyana, Rabindranath Ananda Publisher/ First Publication-2012 / pp. 25

was strongly in favour of work. He did not have a heart to make himself alien to the world. He had to struggle hard for giving rebirth to modern India. In case he was indifferent to the world, it could not have been possible for him to combat 'Sati' and other dreadful omens fatal to Society.¹² Swami Vivekananda, a believer and preacher of the Upaniṣads, was not in the opinion that the world is to be taken as false. Though he was a monk of specified order, he never flew away from the world.⁸ Rather, as per instruction of Ramakrishna Paramahansa Deva, he devoted himself for the sake of the people lying behind in consideration of social and economic status. '*Shiva-gyane jiva seva*'—the noble doctrine uttered by Sri Ramakrishna, was the only path Swamiji followed that brought India to the threshold of a new era.

Mr. Bhowmik alleges that Śaṅkara misinterpreted the Upaniṣads while striving to establish the world as false. Bhowmik gives some examples in favour of his argument. '*Tena tyaktena bhujñīthāḥ*' – the sermon of the Isaponisada means enjoyment by dint of sacrifice. Śaṅkarā interpreted the line as—Leave the world. Again, in the

Isaponisadad, there is a hymn '*īśā vāsyam idaṁ sarvaṁ*'. The word '*Basyam*' denotes ambiguous. It may be referred to as a veil over the body and further it may mean the ability to live. Śaṅkara accepted the first meaning and declared that the whole of the world, being the veil of Maya, is unreal or false. According to Bhowmik, Śaṅkara's interpretation does not follow the observation of the Upaniṣad.

Prof. Bhowmik has observed that the world is a manifestation of the eternal bliss. If we fight shy of the worldly affairs, if we ignore our sensory organs, would it ever be possible for us to realize the intricate? Rabindranath has rightly said, 'the incomparable and mysterious feeling of beauty does not claim anything from us but our free will, and, therefore it murmurs unceasingly—let there be a bridge of happiness between you and me, let there be spontaneity to accept me and my pleasure'. We are a part of this world and our realization deriving from the material world actively helps us form the concept of the earth and the earth beyond. Therefore, we have no other alternative but to accept the

¹² Ibid., p.14

world as 'true' as per the observation of the Science of the Material System.

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There is a saying – where Science ends, Philosophy begins. It is quite natural that men of Physics will not peep into a world where we. But existence of quantum field and its centrifugal forces prove that all on the earth and also in the universe are being originated from the one and only i.e. quantum field. At this point of observation, concept of Brahman and quantum field comes closer and closer.

If we accept dual existence of the source and its elements, we may proclaim that Brahman and the world are true at the same time. Alternatively, if we take the source as prime force then its substances become secondary. Similarly, Śaṅkara realized that Brahman is the primary source and the world has been originated and projected as 'secondary' from the one and only Brahman. It is Brahman that exists in everything, in intricate forms, like the particles (electron, neutron and proton) that exist in each and every earthly object. Therefore, the faculty of taking notice and recognition of the Vedantists and the Physicists do not have any major difference.

Prof. Bhowmik propagates dualism in form of concrete as well as abstract truth. Sri Ramakrishna was of the opinion that the world as projected may be defined as Shakti or Saguna Brahman while the same energy detached from worldly affairs is known as Brahman, the Nirguna. But Acarya Śaṅkara was not in a position to accept this dualism. As truth cannot be divided and bifurcated so it is not at all justified to say that the truth maintains double-standard. Brahman is omnipresent. When it is projected in any form (the world or anything else), it never loses its own entity. When we take a string as a snake out of illusion, the string does not become a snake. Similarly, the sensible world cannot have its separate entity with our varied projection. It is a fact that the world appears to be in a form as per our desire and feeling. If I happily stare at something, it will confer in the same way. If I frown, it will frown in turn. So, it cannot be claimed that worldly affairs are always the same. As because earthly elements vary from man to man so we may not conclude that these are as same as the primal source.

Prof. Bhowmik has opined that Acarya Śaṅkara has defamed the history of India by propagating a theory of negation with regard to the practical world. Mr.

Bhowmik, I doubt, has failed to understand the mode of thinking the Acarya held. We come to know from the history of Śaṅkara's life that he was out and out active in search of the truth and he did not even spare a moment of his life by doing nothing or thinking void or negative. He realized the truth by self-renunciation. It was no knowledge to him derived from mere theory. Instead, by dint of his incomparable Sadhana, he had the awareness that sensibility cannot lead us to the golden path of self-realization and worldly thinking can never make it possible to adjoin us with the eternal. So far, we stick to the material world, so far, we tend to bodily pleasure, we will never be able to make out what Self or Atman is. Upaniṣad does not advise us to continue corporal pleasure as a parallel practice of renunciation. It is not even practicable. If I have a mind to sacrifice, the question of enjoyment does not arise. So, Śaṅkara was not at all faulty while analyzing the term '*Tyakteṇa bhujñīthāḥ*' from the view point of self-renunciation.

When Śaṅkara analyses his theory from ordinary point of view, earthly

elements, either animate or inanimate, are not ignored. When he was compelled to have an argument as regard sexuality, he had to enter the material body of a departed king and to learn from his (king's) wife the ins and outs of sexuality.¹³ If he was adamant in rejecting the worldly affairs, did he do all these things? He did not have the stupidity to ignore the fact but he was very much sure that the concept of Brahman cannot be explored from ordinary point of view. To do this we should have an inner eye, a prolonged practice for detachment of the organs from Self or Atman and to be one with the origin where there is neither duality nor any sort of bifurcation.

When we look at the world from ordinary view-point, so many differences struck us. If I am critical to one, I will find out one's faults innumerable. The practical point of view encourages us to make a difference—good and bad, high and low, rich and poor, aristocrat and vagrant, primitive and modern, modern and post-modern and so on. Where there are differences and oppositeness, it is hardly possible for us to detect the one and only, either quantum

¹³ Swami Apurbananda, Acarya Śaṅkara, Udbodan. p. 85

field or Brahman. When we are in search of One, we must rid of the physical self, otherwise the one will be projected as many and we will never be able to get at the truth. When Sri Ramakrishna touched Narendranath with his holy palm and strengthened him, young Naren felt that there was no separate entity of anything on the earth and everything around him was the imagery of one and only Brahman. Similarly, when we can transform our sense of reality into the Self or Atman, we will come to know that there is no duality on the earth, everything is the one and same and the world has no separate identity apart from Brahman or the Supreme Being either formed or unformed.

There is another way to show the falsity of the world as it seems to appear before us. We have earlier told that the world is manifestation of the Reality, the Being or Brahman as we call it, which, in other words, is Sat. When the reality is rightly comprehended, it will be manifested that the so-called world never existed in the past, does not exist so far and will never exist again. If we take the example of a conch-shell and a piece of silver, we may clarify our stand. When we pick up a conch-shell comprehending that to be a piece of

silver and later come to know that it was not at all silver, the very entity of silver becomes fake to us. That means when we would be able to get at the Truth or Ultimate Reality, the projected view will ultimately vanish and it will have no subsistence to us. Similarly, when the Brahman, the Being or Reality, is once recognized, the conviction comes that the apparent world never existed and will not exist further.

As and when the Supreme Being is known to us through immense practice and intense experiment, it will never again be falsified by later experience or other means of proof. A thing is said to be true so long it remains uncontroversial and unabated. Absence of right knowledge causes illusion that disappears at the dawn of wisdom. Therefore, we are to stick to the observation of Śāṅkara in connection with Monism that places Brahman at the centre of everything on the earth and beyond.

On conclusion, we are to express our concrete view that absence of right knowledge in form of self-realization arising out of self-renunciation will ever be liable to mislead us to the path of duality. Truth is one—undivided, non-contradictory, unabated and uncontroversial. The theory

'Brahman Satya and Jagat Satya' should, therefore, be rejected on the basis of the argument as Śāṅkara held that Brahman and the world cannot be true at the same time, instead, Brahman is true even when it is being projected as the world or anything else. When we see anything around us, experience something from our everyday life or realize something profound, we must keep in mind that all the objects and experience, thoughts and realization are the sum total of Brahman, the only Being, that exists eternally without having any formal change or decay or destruction. We may quote Swami Vivekananda as he says— "We are in reality that Infinite Being, and our personalities represent so many channels through which this Infinite Reality is manifesting itself; and the whole mass of changes which we call evolution is brought about by the soul trying to manifest more and more of its infinite energy. We cannot stop anywhere on this side of the Infinite; our power, and blessedness, and wisdom, cannot but grow into the Infinite. Infinite power and existence and blessedness are ours, and we have not to acquire them; they

are our own, and we have only to manifest them."¹⁴

This the sum and substance of Monism as realized by the Rishis of ancient India, by Acarya Śāṅkarā in medieval India and that by Swami Vivekanda in recent past. Advaita *Vendānta* is not at all imaginative. Rather, it is the only Reality that explains the Self, Morality, the universe and the concept of Brahman as persists in varied particles prevailing on the earth.

In conclusion it must be said that Śāṅkarā's doctrine is to be followed by self-realization and self-renunciation. So long we are attached to worldly affairs, we cannot make out what Śāṅkarā says. Śāṅkarā did not admit the material world because he knew so long we tend to sensibility it would not be possible for us to realize Brahman. When we are able to make ourselves detached from sensibility, at that very moment Brahman i.e. pure consciousness will be revealed to us. This is why I think Śāṅkara's school of thinking is very much right from the view point of a person who has overcome passion and bodily needs.

¹⁴ Lokeswarananda, Swami (ed.), *Swami Vivekanda: His Life and Message*, The Ramakrishna Mission Institute of Culture, kol-29, March-2010, p.16

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